

ANALYSIS OF SHEROBOD QUARTZ SAND BY INFRARED SPECTROSCOPIC METHOD

Khidir Adinaev¹, Zulaykha Kadirova¹, Rustam Kadirov²

¹*UzR FA Institute of General and Inorganic Chemistry, Республика Узбекистан, г. Ташкент. E-mail: Xidir72@mail.ru*

²*Termiz Institute of Engineering and Technology, Республика Узбекистан, г. Ташкент*

Abstract. The main components of glass are oxygen compounds. It has been found that unenriched quartz sand can be added as glass components by purification and enrichment of various additives. Sherabad quartz sand was analyzed by infrared spectroscopic method and its properties were studied.

Key words: raw material, quartz sand, PbO-SiO₂ system, oxygen compounds, amorphous substance, glass, IR spectroscopic method.

In the Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, among other things, the tasks of "...increasing the competitiveness of the national economy, ...reducing the consumption of energy and resources in the economy, widely introducing energy-saving technologies in production..." are defined. In this regard, in order to provide the construction network with high-quality materials and constructions that increase the energy efficiency of buildings, using local raw materials, the composition of glass materials with specified properties and high performance, and the development of energy-saving technology of its production are considered to be of significant scientific importance.

Glass is an amorphous substance formed by heating and cooling a mixture of glass-forming components (silicon, boron, aluminum, phosphorus, germanium oxides) and oxides of metals (lithium, potassium, sodium, calcium, magnesium, lead, etc.) is a brittle material. When glass is heated, it does not liquefy and harden at a certain temperature, like crystalline substances, but gradually changes from a

solid state to an elastic soft state and finally to a liquid state. When the liquefied glass solution is cooled, it first changes to a plastic state within a certain temperature range, and then hardens. We know that glass is an amorphous substance, while glass is usually brittle and transparent.

The main components of glass are oxygen compounds. Silicon, lead, boron, sodium oxides form glass. Based on the PbO-SiO_2 system, without additives and with the addition of B_2O_3 , Na_2O , CaO and Al_2O_3 , it forms glass very easily.

According to the use, it is divided into construction glass, architectural construction glass, automotive glass, thermally stable glass, chemical laboratory glass, medical glass, optical glass, electrovacuum glass, light engineering glass, as well as glass fiber and glass plastics. Ionizing ray shielding glass, penetrating radiation indicator glass, variable light transmissive photochromic glass, glass used as laser materials, fusible glass, etc. is produced.

Glass is baked in industry mainly in bath furnaces and special steam furnaces. The glass baking process includes liquefaction, clarification (removal of air and other gases), homogenization and cooling of the glass mass. Glass is fired at 1400-1450°C, clarified and homogenized at 1460-1500°C, cooled at 1200-1300°C. Forming and making articles from it is done by pressing, blowing and stretching.

It was done by wetting method with the use of ethyl alcohol in mixing the sample. In the picture below, the structural properties of Sherabad quartz sand were studied using the infrared spectroscopic method.

Picture. Infrared spectrum of Sherabad quartz sand

That is, the vibrational peak of $3451,12 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the infrared spectrum of Sherabad quartz sand corresponds to Al-OH valence vibrations. Also called OH group vibrations. $1051,57 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to Si-O valence vibrations and O-H deformation vibrations. $881,61$ and $778,21 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ correspond to Si-O-Si valence vibrations, considering the peak of residual complexes. $694,67$ to $462,78 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to O-Si-O valence vibrations and Si-O-Si deformation vibrations [1-2].

In conclusion, according to the infrared spectroscopic analysis of Sherabad quartz sand, it was found that unenriched sand can be added as glass components after purification from various additives and enrichment.

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